

TAILORING MMC MICROSTRUCTURES

H. X. Peng*

Advanced Composite Centre for Innovation and Science, Department of Aerospace Engineering, University of Bristol, University Walk, Bristol, BS8 1TR, UK.

* H.X.Peng@Bristol.ac.uk

SUMMARY

The aim in designing composite materials is to combine both the matrix and reinforcement properties to provide high performance. The success in exploiting the high strength of the reinforcement is over-shadowed by the failure to exploit the matrix ductility. The present research work has demonstrated that composite properties can be enhanced by tailoring the reinforcement architectures namely *reinforcement morphology* and *reinforcement spatial distribution* in stead of pursuing a homogeneous arrangements.

Keywords: Inhomogeneity; MMC Microstructures; Mechanical properties; Reinforcement

INTRODUCTION

Despite many favourable attributes, such as high specific strength and stiffness, superior wear resistance etc, discontinuously reinforced metal matrix composites (MMCs) tend to exhibit low ductility and damage tolerance even when a highly ductile matrix material such as aluminium is employed [1, 2]. A better combination of strength and damage tolerance is required if such materials are to be widely used in structural components [2].

Looking at the context of MMCs development, for several decades, the main research activities in discontinuous MMCs have been focused on the production of a *homogeneous* distribution of the reinforcing phase in the matrix. MMC microstructures have been tailored to a certain extent by altering volume fraction (V_f), size and aspect ratio of the reinforcing phases. This is based on the philosophy that damage-related properties can be improved by delaying crack initiation. However, both the contiguity model [3] and preliminary experimental results have shown that a tailored *inhomogeneous* microstructure with varying degree of continuity of the reinforcing phase will be more effective for overall property improvement. In contrast to the majority of activities in DMMCs research that have been focused on the production of a homogeneous distribution of the reinforcement in the matrix, two innovative approaches, namely *designing reinforcement morphology* and *tailoring reinforcement distribution*, have been adopted to design DMMC microstructures with better properties combination. This offers several opportunities to design the MMC microstructures for performance enhancement.

NEW APPROACHES, RESULTLS AND DISCUSSIONS

One of the opportunities is morphological design of the reinforcement, notably that inspired by biomimetic approach [4]. Experiments were carried out to create inter-fibre links that are believed to be beneficial to increasing the fibre pull-out energy. A phosphate binder was produced that gave strong inter-fibre cross-links as shown in Fig.1 where SAFFIL Al_2O_3 short fibres were used. Composites were fabricated by squeeze casting of the preform with aluminium alloy. Property testing was performed on as-cast MMCs. The results indicated that the composites reinforced with the cross-linked fibre preform had higher tensile strength

(UTS) relative to the conventional fibre preform reinforced composites without any sacrifice to the ductility and in plane elastic modulus at a given fibre volume fraction.

In addition to deliberate design of reinforcement morphology, another opportunity to address those problems is to tailor the reinforcement distribution. This microstructural design originating from theoretical predictions is now becoming recognised. In contrast to the uniform distribution of the reinforcing fibres, short fibre agglomerates were fabricated as shown in Fig.2. These fibre agglomerates were subsequently used to make composites by squeeze casting.

Fig.1. SEM micrograph of cross-linked fibres in the preform ($V_f=10\%$)

Fig. 2 SEM micrograph of fibre agglomerates produced from SAFFIL alumina shot fibres.

Three-point loading tests were performed on notched samples. The results indicated that the composite reinforced with fibre agglomerates exhibited a much higher energy absorbing capability (characterized by the area below the load-displacement curve) than that with the conventional fibre preform. The composite also exhibited higher UTS but lower strain at fracture than those of the composite with the conventional preform as revealed by preliminary tensile testing results.

According to the contiguity model, a three-dimensional network distribution of the reinforcement might result in an even higher strengthening effect than the reinforcement agglomerate does. A cellular short fibre preform is also developed where a three-dimensionally continuous fibre network was created leaving highly inter-connected pores. High strength and stiffness of the composite are expected. In addition, due to the highly inter-connected pores in the cellular preform, the continuity of the matrix phase in the filled composite would be high. As a consequence, a better damage tolerance of the composite can also be expected.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

HXP thanks the support from the U.K. Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council and the Chinese National Programme of Introducing Talents of Discipline to Universities.

References

- [1] A. Kelly and C. Zweben, *Comprehensive Composite Materials* - 3, Elsevier, Oxford, 2000.
- [2] T.W. Clyne, P.J. Withers, *An introduction to Metal Matrix Composites*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 1997.
- [3] Z. Fan, *Phil. Mag.* 1996; 73:1663.
- [4] B.L. Zhou, *JOM*, 1994:57.